

Causality and Persistence

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Abstract

This work explores the relations between causality and counterfactual implication and proposes a counterfactual theory of causality. The proposed model permits a richer formalization than Lewis' (1973) counterfactual analysis of causality. The first objection to Lewis' theory, that reducing the notion of causation to the notion of similarity between possible worlds amounts to reducing a hard problem to an harder one, is surpassed eliminating the notion of similarity between accessible worlds and introducing the notion of similarity between what is defined as possible histories. The epiphenomena problem and the effects problem, approached with the proposed notion of causality, are minimized. Some notions of persistence using the theory of causality proposed are defined. The presented temporal language *LT*, a first order language, includes the notions defined of persistence and counterfactual implication.

1 Introduction

The link between the problem of persistence and causality in the field of artificial intelligence has been recognized for quite some time. Kautz [1], for example, in his work on logic of persistence, states that “the incapacity is ontological: we can not handle properly the persistence while we have not a richest theory of causality”. Philosophically there are two ways of understanding the problem of persistence: (i) objects have temporal parts and only part of an object that persists, called the current part, is present at every time in its existence over that time and (ii) objects persist over time because it is fully present in each time in which they exist. We can also affirm on persistence, like Kautz, that “Given that no relevant action, or perhaps no action at all, occurred over a stretch of time, one may need to infer that certain facts do not change their truth value”. One of the objectives of this work is to search, within of the proposed causality theory, definitions of persistence that can meet the three forms presented here.

The view on causality is mostly divided in those who analyze causal influence as some sort of probabilistic relationship and those who analyze causal influence as a kind of counterfactual relationship. It is known that the paradigms of machine learning that basically rely on correlations present serious limitations on their power and performance. Such systems without causal reasoning tools cannot serve as the basis for strong AI [2] and [3]. Pearl [4], for example, acknowledging this, abandoned the empiricist tradition in which “causality simply provides useful ways of abbreviating and organizing intricate patterns of probabilistic relationships” and began to use counterfactuals to achieve results that enable computers to causal thinking. The second and main objective of this work is to propose a theory of causality based on counterfactuals. The starting point for the proposed theory of causality is the seminal work of Lewis [5].

Section 2 contains the choices related to the temporal representation, the structure of the historical process and entities associated to time (objects, worlds, events, ...).

The proposed notion of causality is given in section 3. Lewis' work [5] on causality has influenced the presented notion; however, the notions differ considerably. Lewis exploits one of the definitions of causality given by Hume [6] to define causal dependence; in the proposed notion, Hume's definition is directly used. Lewis considers as primitive a comparative and overall relation of similarity among possible worlds; in the proposed notion, a distinct notion of similarity is used, not being a measure of proximity among possible worlds but among what has been defined in section 2 as possible histories. The problems of the epiphenomena and of the effects, not solved in Lewis' theory, are examined. The lack of precision of the similarity notion existing in Lewis' work is minimized; an algorithm to determine similar histories is proposed.

Definitions about persistence and action are provided in section 4.

Section 5, a language of first order is defined that contains explicitly reference to temporal instants or intervals and that includes the proposed notions of persistence and counterfactuals.

Section 6 presents results with the proposed theory.

2 From Possible Worlds to Events

2.1 Worlds, Histories and Processes

Let the definitions be as follows:

Definition 2.1 Let T be a totally ordinated set, with a first element, satisfying to

$$T = \{t_0, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_i, \dots\} \quad i \in N \quad (1)$$

where

$$0 \leq t_i < t_{i+1} \quad i \in N \quad \text{and} \quad t_i \in R \quad (2)$$

N is the set of natural numbers and R is the set of real numbers. The set T is denominated as temporal set.

The succession of $t_0, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_i, \dots$ is denominated as *temporal succession*. Each element of T is a *time instant*. A subset $\{t_i, \dots, t_k, \dots, t_j\}$ of T , in a such manner that $t_{k-1} < t_k < t_{k+1}$, is denominated *temporal interval*.

Definition 2.2 Let W be a set with more than one element. Representing by R the set of transitions from elements of W to elements of W , let U be a set whose elements, u , are in the form

$$(w_0, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_i, \dots) \quad (3)$$

where

$$w_i \in W, \quad i \in N \quad (4)$$

w_0 is a possible initial condition, w_i corresponds to the instant t_i e w_{i+1} is a transition value of w_i by R . U is denominated the set of the possible histories for W and R .

The elements of the set W are denominated *possible worlds*. The Figures 1 to 3 illustrate the set U . In the figures, to each element, w , of the set of possible worlds, W , corresponds a dot in the ordinated axis. The Figure 1 shows a history, u_y ; in this case when the world in t_6 becomes the same world that exists in t_0 , the succession of worlds from t_0 to t_5 (that is, w_2, w_6, w_5, w_4, w_7 and w_3) repeats from w_6 . The Figure 2 presents two possible histories, u_y and u_z , in which the time is branched. The histories u_y and u_z diverge in t_2 ; in the instant t_3 u_y is w_6 while u_z is w_3 . In the Figure 3 the set U is $\{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6\}$; there exists the convergence of u_1 and u_2 at t_1 and convergence of u_1, u_2 and u_3 at t_6 . In the Figure 3 there are ramifications in t_2 and t_5 and in the instants t_3 and t_4 the history u_6 crosses the histories u_1 and u_2 the same way that u_y "crosses" u_z between t_3 and t_4 in the Figure 2.

The set U shows the worlds that exist, can exist or could have existed in any element of the temporal succession T . However U informs anything about if, to $t_k \in T$ and $u_x \in U$, the world $u_x(t_k)$ is realized or not and, if it is not realized, if it can or not be realized. Let t^* be the present time; the subset of T such that $t_i < t^*$ is the past and the subset of T such that $t_i > t^*$ is the future. Let us assume that

Premise 2.1 For each $t \leq t^*$ one, and only one, of the possible worlds of W is realized. The realized world in t is represented by $w(t, t^*)$.

Definition 2.3 Let be the subset of U whose elements comply with the condition

$$u(t) = w(t, t^*) \quad \text{for} \quad t \leq t^* \quad (5)$$

These elements, that receive the notation $u_k^P(t)$, are denominated as possible realizable histories in $t_k = t^*$.

Figure 1: A possible history

Figure 2: Two possible histories with branched time

Figure 3: A set of possible histories, U

The set of all $u_k^P(t)$ is represented by U_k^P . All the elements belonging to U and not belonging to U_k^P are unrealizable histories in t_k and are represented by $u_k^N(t)$ and the set of these elements by U_k^N . Generally, while the process is being realized (the value of t^* increasing) more elements cease to belong to by U_k^P and pass to belong to by U_k^N . While the realizations take place what is potential decreases. The Figure 4 shows a set U_k^P . The possible worlds for immediate successor of $w(t^*, t^*)$ are the worlds of the elements of U_k^P in t , where t is the immediate successor of t^* .

Figure 4: A set of possible realizable histories

Definition 2.4 Let be the set U_k^P . If this set has a single element, then the process in realization is a deterministic process starting from at t_k ; otherwise, the process in realization is a non-deterministic process.

U_k^P given in the Figure 4 is a example of non-deterministic process, considering the branches for $t > t_k$. For each t that succeeds t_j anything realized does not exist, there existing only possibilities and potentiality.

Premise 2.2 A possible world w is constituted by interrelated objects.

Definition 2.5 Let O_W be the set of existing objects in the elements of W and $o_a \in O_W$ and $o_b \in O_W$ two existing objects in $u(t)$. The objects o_a and o_b coexist in a given temporal interval of $u(t)$, when, for all t belonging to the interval, if one of them exists the other object exists too.

Definition 2.6 Let A be a subset of U . A property existent in $u(t)$, for all t and u of the subset A , is denominated invariant property in A .

Definition 2.7 Let t_j be an element of T and $u_x(t)$ belonging to U . The set formed by all the elements of U equal to $u_x(t)$ for $t \leq t_j$ is represented by U_j^x and its elements by $u_j^x(t)$.

2.2 Events

Intuitively, event means something involving change. A change requires an interval of the temporal succession. Within this interval one or more objects can exist, cease to exist or pass through modifications.

Definition 2.8 *An event is characterized by:*

- (a) *a subset not empty of U , denominated A ;*
- (b) *a temporal interval (t_i, t_j) ;*
- (c) *a subset not empty of O_W , denominated B ;*
- (d) *each object of B exists (or comes into existence) and it changes the same way in the interval (t_i, t_j) in all elements of A ;*
- (e) *the elements of U that satisfy (d) belong to A ;*

An event is represented by $e(t_i, t_j)$.

A realized event requires in addition that the temporal interval (t_i, t_j) being such that $t_j \leq t^*$ and $A = U_j^x$. Let $e_a(t_i, t_j)$ and $e_b(t_k, t_l)$ be distinct events existing in a history u , if $t_i = t_k$ and $t_j = t_l$ then $e_a(t_i, t_j)$ and $e_b(t_k, t_l)$ are *simultaneous events*.

The model assumes a temporal beginning. However, using the notion of state (state incorporates all the past history) we can associate to the first element of T the conditions of a given temporal instant, for cases without temporal beginning.

The set U is a manner of providing the relations of accessibility. Observe that this approach differs from Lewis' [5]; in that logic, the possible worlds are "parallel" in time, all of them sharing the same time interpretation. The set U specifies (i) the worlds of possible existence in any element of the temporal set T and (ii) for any world of possible existence w for an element t of T , which possible worlds for the immediate successor of t to which w has access.

In the Figure 4, up to the element t_j , the histories u_3 , u_4 , u_5 and u_6 are equal, for the immediate successor of t_j the histories branching in two sets. A branch can be attributed to chance or to free will. The two are logically possible and one does not exclude the other.

3 The Proposed Notion of Causality

3.1 Accessibility and Similarity

Access from a possible world to another depends on the set U and the realization state of the process.

Definition 3.1 *Let $u(t)$ be an element of U_i^x . A world w is accessible from $u(t_i)$ if w is in some element of U_i^x at the instant t_j , where t_j is the immediate successor of t_i .*

The Figure 5 shows a W with only four possible worlds; the arrows indicate for each $w_i \in W$ the elements of W which w_i can access immediately. From this definition we have that the accessibility from a world at a given possible history is more restrictive than the accessibility of an element to another in the set W . The relationship between worlds that are accessible is not necessarily transitive. A possible history u_x can contain the worlds w_1 , w_2 and w_3 with w_2 accessible from w_1 and w_3 accessible from w_2 ; another history of u_y can have the world w_1 and w_3 and have not the world w_3 accessible from w_2 .

Let be a possible history u_x . Let's suppose that there exists a proposition p that is true in u_x at the interval (t_i, t_j) . Intuitively, a possible history similar to u_x for p false in (t_i, t_j) , can be understood as a history u with p false in (t_i, t_j) and such that the number and the importance of the propositions of u whose truth values are different of u_x are minimum for the interval (t_0, t_j) . This notion of similarity assumes that a potential history is described by the propositions being true or false in it.

Definition 3.2 *Let p be the proposition true in the interval (t_i, t_j) [or instant t_j] in u_x . A history $u \in U_0^x$ with $\neg p$ true in (t_i, t_j) is similar to u_x if*

Figure 5: Example of immediate access between elements of W

(a) is equal to u_x for $t_0 \leq t < t_n$ and

(b) there is no element with $\neg p$ true in (t_i, t_j) [or instant t_j] which have a t_n greater.

If there does not exist in U_0^x an element similar to u_x then a history $u \in (U - U_0^x)$ with $\neg p$ true at (t_i, t_j) [or instant t_j] is similar to u_x .

Let be represented by S the set not empty of elements of U similar in relation to u_x for p false at the interval (t_i, t_j) or instant t_j . In order to obtain S let be:

Algorithm 3.1

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data  $\{t_0, \dots, t_j\}, u_x, p, (t_i, t_j)$  [or  $t_i$ ],  $U, U_0^x$ 
 $k := i$ 
 $S := \{\emptyset\}$ 
while  $S = \{\emptyset\}$  or  $k > 0$  do
   $k := k - 1$ 
  find  $U_k^x$ 
  find  $S$ , the subset of  $U_k^x$  such that in its elements  $\neg p$  be true at  $(t_i, t_j)$  [or  $t_i$ ]
if  $S := \{\emptyset\}$  then
   $k := k - 1$ 
  find  $S$ , the subset of  $(U - U_0^x)$  in which elements  $\neg p$  be true at  $(t_i, t_j)$  [or  $t_i$ ]
if  $S := \{\emptyset\}$  then
   $U$  does not have  $\neg p$  true at  $(t_i, t_j)$  [or  $t_i$ ]
  
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Let us denominate as *critical instant* of S the instant t_k with k equal to the output value of the algorithm 3.1 and the interval (t_k, t_j) as *critical interval*.

The procedure using the algorithm 3.1 finds S under the condition of being maximum the interval from t_0 to t_k in which the elements of S are equal to u_x ; it will be denominated as critical interval procedure; or briefly, CIP. In order to illustrate this proposal, let's consider the following scenery:

Scenery 3.1

At 8:17, on August 6, 1945 Hiroshima is destroyed by the nuclear bomb explosion thrown by the Enola Gay seconds before.

What kind of world is similar to the scenery for the non occurrence of nuclear explosion? Although greatly improbable, the bomb neutron source could be generating, at the moment of detonation, a rate so small of neutrons that it practically would result in a non nuclear explosion (the bomb exploded due to the detonation of the chemical explosive contained within). In this similar world the city would not be destroyed. The CIP provides a S . Another way of the nuclear explosion not occurring in the city would be if the crew of the aircraft had not decided to throw the bomb in Hiroshima, either to attack the secondary target or for some other reason. This way does not belong to S , provided that the crew's decision of not throwing the bomb occurs before the critical interval. The crew's decision of not throwing the bomb is much more probable than this way of nuclear explosion failure, however the mode of failure due to the neutrons insufficiency in the detonations provides what is looked for: a possible similar history.

Figure 6: Destroyed Hiroshima

Let p be a true proposition about the event $e(t_i, t_j)$ occurring in u_x ; in Figure 7 the history possible with true $\neg p$ similar to u_x is u_y , given that $t_j - t_k$ is less than $t_j - t_l$. Figure 8 is an example in which no history belonging to U_0^x has $\neg p$ true; in this case, the similar history is u .

3.2 Causes and Effects

Definition 3.3 Let O be any non empty set such that each element of it is a proposition that affirms or denies the existence or property of objects belonging to O_W . A set O refers to a possible world, temporal instant, temporal interval or event and all elements of O are true for the possible world, temporal instant, temporal interval or event considered.

Definition 3.4 Let be

- O_a and O_b as defined in 3.3;
- represented by $p(a)$ either a proposition on the existence of O_a in $u(t_j)$ or a proposition on the existence of the set O_a in some world of u at the interval (t_i, t_j) or a proposition on the existence of O_a in the event $e_a(t_i, t_j)$ in u ;

Figure 7: Similarity in U_0^x

Figure 8: Similarity out of U_0^x

- represented by $p(b)$ either a proposition on the existence of O_b in $u(t_k)$ or a proposition on the existence of the set O_b in some world of u at the interval (t_k, t_l) or a proposition on the existence of O_b in the event $e_b(t_k, t_l)$ in u ;
- t_k strictly preceded by t_j (that is, $t_k < t_j$);
- represented by u_z any element of U similar in relation to u for $\neg p(a)$ true.

The existence affirmed in $p(a)$, is a cause of the existence affirmed in $p(b)$, when

- (i) $p(a)$ and $p(b)$ are true;
- (i) $p(b)$ is false in all u_z .

Definition 3.5 If

- $p(a)$ and $p(b)$ are as defined in 3.3 and, consequently, $p(a)$ is a cause of $p(b)$;
- the subset O_n of O_a is withdrawn, resulting $O_{a'}$;
- the proposition on the existence of $O_{a'}$ is represented by $p(a')$;
- $p(a')$ is not a cause of $p(b)$;
- the proposition on the existence of O_n is represented by $p(n)$;

then $p(n)$ is a necessary cause of $p(b)$ considering $p(a)$.

Definition 3.6 If

- $p(a)$ and $p(b)$ are as defined in 3.3 and, consequently, $p(a)$ is a cause of $p(b)$;
- O_n is a subset of O_a ;
- the proposition on the existence of O_n is represented by $p(n)$;
- $p(n)$ is necessary cause of $p(b)$ considering $p(a)$;
- part of the elements of O_n is substituted by one or more different elements, resulting $O_{a''}$;
- the proposition on the existence of $O_{a''}$ is represented by $p(s)$;
- $p(s)$ is a cause of $p(b)$;

then $p(a)$ is a sufficient cause of $p(b)$.

Definition 3.7 $p(b)$ is an effect of $p(a)$ when $p(a)$ is a cause of $p(b)$.

Definition 3.8 It is said that x is an absolute necessary cause for y when there exists more than a sufficient cause for the effect y and x is a necessary cause for all the sufficient causes for y .

Definition 3.9 Let $p(a)$ be a cause of $p(b)$ in u_x . It is said that $p(a)$ is a contingent cause of $p(b)$ when there exists some element of the set U_j^x with $p(a)$ true and $p(b)$ false.

Let us notice that, after using the algorithm 3.1, if U does not have a possible history with $\neg p$ true at (t_i, t_j) [or t_i] then p is not a cause for anything.

In definition 3.4 the cause event entirely precedes the effect event. The relation *entirely precedes* is one of the twelve possible relations of temporal positioning between two events [7]. The possible relations are shown in Figure 8. The current interval shown in figure is considered as corresponding to the cause event. The relation (H) satisfies the requirement of the definition 3.4.

Definition 3.10 Let be

- (a) a proposition $p(a)$ about $e_a(t_1, t_2)$ in u_x ;
- (b) a proposition $p(b)$ about $e_b(t_3, t_4)$ in u_x ;
- (c) a proposition $p(r)$ about $e_r(t_i, t_j)$ in u_x with $t_i \succeq t_1$ and $t_j \preceq t_2$;
- (d) a proposition $p(s)$ about $e_s(t_k, t_l)$ in u_x with $t_k \succeq t_3$ and $t_l \preceq t_4$.

If $p(r)$ is a cause of $p(s)$, then $p(b)$ depends on causal mode of $p(a)$.

With the definition, the relations (F) and (K) in the Figure 8 are not admitted for causal dependence (the current interval corresponds to the cause).

The Figure 10 shows an example of causal dependence where the existence of the Tower 1 of World Trade Center depends on causal mode of the existence of Al-Qaeda.

3.3 Spurious Causes

Regarding the theory of causality proposed by Lewis [5] there exist the following objections:

- (a) The difficulty of distinguishing real causes of epiphenomena.
- (b) According to the definition of causality, all event is cause of itself, existing nothing that excludes the circular causality or prevents the possibility of an effect precedes its cause.

Figure 9: Possible relations between two distinct intervals

Figure 10: Example of causal dependence

To present the problem of epiphenomena let be the following version of Lewis' definition [5] of *causal dependence*.

Definition 3.11 *Let e_a and e_b be two possible distinct events and the propositions $p(e_a)$ and $p(e_b)$ that are true in all the worlds and only in them where e_a and e_b respectively occur. The event $p(e_b)$ depends causally on $p(e_a)$ if and only if the counterfactuals*

$$p(e_a) \quad \square \rightarrow \quad p(e_b) \tag{6}$$

and

$$\neg p(e_a) \quad \square \rightarrow \quad \neg p(e_b) \tag{7}$$

were true.

The problem of epiphenomena [5]:

Problem 3.1

- (i) *suppose that e_c causes first e_e and afterwards e_f and that e_e does not cause e_f ;*
- (ii) *suppose (afterwards) that e_c could not have failed to cause e_e and that e_f could not have been caused otherwise than by e_c .*

Then there exists a causal dependence of e_f in relation to e_e , contradicting the assumption that e_e does not cause e_f .

Regarding the counterfactual analysis a similar difficulty is the problem of the effects [5]:

Problem 3.2

- (i) *let's suppose that the event e_a causes a subsequent event e_b and that e_b does not cause e_a ;*
- (ii) *let's suppose (further) that e_a could have not failed to cause e_b .*

From (ii) let's have that if e_b had not occurred, then e_a would not occur; therefore existing a causal dependence of e_a in relation to e_b and contradicting the hypothesis that e_b does not cause e_a .

The basic difficulty concerning the above-mentioned problem of the effects is in its own formulation: the notion of cause of Lewis excludes temporal orientation. This means that there is dependence from e_b to e_a and that *causal dependence* (as defined by Lewis [5]) means that there is a contradiction to say that e_b *not cause* e_a .

As for the problem of epiphenomena, the only dependence on the theory proposed here between e_e and e_f is that both are effects of e_c . Figure 9 presents the case described in items (i) and (ii) of the problem 3.2; note that $p(e)$ does not cause $p(f)$ (the critical instant is t_j) and $p(c)$ is the cause of $p(e)$ and of $p(f)$ (the critical moment is t_i). There is, however, the case in which e_e is the effect of e_c , e_f is the effect of e_c and e_e is a cause of e_f as defined in 3.3 section; Figure 10 shows this case. Considering this let be:

Definition 3.12 *It is said that e_e is a prima facie cause of e_f in u_x when (i) by definition 3.4 e_e is a cause of e_f in u_x , (ii) by definition 3.4 e_c is cause of e_e in u_x and e_c is the cause of e_f in u_x and (iii) the two critical instants - obtained by determining with the algorithm 3.1 similar stories to u_x for $\neg e_c$, for $\neg e_e$ and for $\neg e_f$ - are equal.*

4 Persistence and Action

4.1 Persistence

To persist implies to perdure, to remain, to be constant, to continue to be. Persistence involves temporal interval and continuity of being, existing or doing at the interval. As here considered, what persist at some temporal interval is a proposition, and what is constant along the time is a truth value of the proposition. McDermoth [8] has proposed the following notion of persistence:

Figure 11: The problem 3.2 in U

Figure 12: *Prima facie* cause in U

“A fact p persists from s with a lifetime r , if in all chronicles it remains true until r has gone or until it ceases of to be true.”

In this definition s is a state. The states are partially ordinate; each state possesses an occurrence time, a real number denominated its data. The states are arranged in chronicles. A chronicle is a completely ordinate set of states, extending themselves endlessly throughout the time. This McDermoth’s definition has influenced the following definitions:

Definition 4.1 A proposition p persists in u_x in the interval (t_k, t) if its truth value is the same in all the instants of the interval.

Definition 4.2 A proposition p persists in U_k^x at the interval (t_k, t) if p persists for all u belonging to U_k^x at the interval (t_k, t) .

Figure 13 gives an example. The proposition p persists in the interval (t_i, t_k) and it persists in u_x in the interval (t_i, t_m) .

Figure 13: A example of persistence in U_i^x

Definition 4.3 A proposition p possibly persists in U_k^x at the interval (t_k, t) if U_k^x has more than one element and p persists at (t_k, t) in some u belonging to U_k^x .

Definition 4.4 A proposition p probably persists at the interval (t_k, t) in U_k^x if (i) p persists possibly at the interval and (ii) the subset of U_k^x formed by elements persisting at the interval (t_k, t) , probably contains the possible history u to be realized.

Considering what is set out in section 3 and in this section, be the following statement:

Problem 4.1 Given a proposition p , the set U_k^x and a set of events occurring at u_x in the interval (t_i, t_j) , where at least one event starts at t_i and at least one event ends at t_j with $t_k > t_j$, what can be said about the effect of the set of events on the persistence of p in the (t_k, t) ?

This problem involves the notions of causality and persistence; its solution and associated issues require the use of the notion of causality: (i) is the set of events occurring necessary and/or sufficient for p to persist in U_k^x in the interval? and (ii) is a non-empty subset of the set of occurred events cause of the persistence (or not) of the proposition p in the interval (t_k, t) ?

4.2 Action

In addition to the above-proposed notions of persistence, a notion of action is necessary. An action is normally understood as the act or manner of acting or the result of the actuation. Among the meanings of acting there are the following: (i) process arising from the nature or will of a being, the agent, and from which results the creation or modification of the reality (ii) the course of this process, activity and (iii) result or effect from this process. Hereby, the following general definition is adopted:

Definition 4.5 *An action is an event whose existence is a (necessary and/or sufficient) cause. It is denominated as possible action or realized action for possible event or realized event, respectively.*

To elucidate the proposed notions of persistence, let's consider the following system, where the objectives are achieved through a sequence (not commutative) of actions:

Scenery 4.1

Let's consider the robot's hand and the configuration of blocks shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Robot's hand and blocks

Let us use *STRIPS*. The predicates are: $CLEAR(x)$ means that the block x has its top free, i.e., there does not exist another block on it; $ON(x,y)$ means that the block x is on (and in contact with) the block y ; $ONTABLE(x)$ means that the block x is on (and in contact with) the table; $HANDEEMPTY$ has the value T when the robot's hand is empty; $HOLDING(x)$ means that robot's hand is holding x . The set of actions for the robot is

1. pickup(x)

P & D: $ONTABLE(x)$, $CLEAR(x)$, $HANDEEMPTY$
A: $HOLDING(x)$

2. putdown(x)

P & D: $HOLDING(x)$
A: $ONTABLE(x)$, $CLEAR(x)$, $HANDEEMPTY$

3. stack(x,y)

P & D: $HOLDING(x)$, $CLEAR(y)$
A: $HANDEEMPTY$, $ON(x,y)$, $CLEAR(x)$

4. unstack(x,y)

P & D: $HANDEEMPTY$, $CLEAR(x)$, $ON(x,y)$

A: HOLDING(x), CLEAR(y)

Let us suppose that $U_i^x = \{u_x, u_y\}$ and the difference between $u(t_k)$ and $u(t_{k+1})$ with $k \geq i$ and $u(t_k) \in U_i^x$ corresponds to an action belonging to the set

$$\{pickup(x), putdown(x), stack(x, y), unstack(x, y)\} \quad (8)$$

Let $u_x(t_i)$ be the state described in Figure 14 and the sequence of actions beginning in t_i :

$$(t_i, unstack(A, B)), (t_{i+1}, putdown(A)), (t_{i+2}, unstack(B, C)), (t_{i+3}, stack(B, A)), \\ (t_{i+4}, unstack(C, D)), (t_{i+5}, stack(C, B)), (t_{i+6}, pickup(D)) \quad (9)$$

Considering the definition 4.2 let's have that $ONTABLE(D)$ persists in the interval (t_i, t_{i+5}) in U_i^x . The definition 4.1, not so restrictive as 4.2 with respect to the time interval in which p persisted, is illustrated in the following sequence of u_y :

$$(t_i, unstack(A, B)), (t_{i+1}, stack(A, E)), (t_{i+2}, unstack(B, C)), (t_{i+3}, stack(B, A)), \\ (t_{i+4}, unstack(C, D)), (t_{i+5}, stack(C, B)), (t_{i+6}, unstack(F, G)), \\ (t_{i+7}, stack(F, C)), (t_{i+8}, pickup(D)) \quad (10)$$

By this sequence of actions, $ONTABLE(D)$ persisted in u_y in the interval (t_i, t_{i+7}) .

5 The Language LT

The language LT is a first order language whose formulas belonging to the minimum set contain explicit reference to the temporal instants or intervals. Its structure is based on Bell's QTK language [9].

The notions of counterfact and persistence are included in LT language.

5.1 Syntax

Let be

T Set of constant symbols.

O_W Set of constant symbols disjoint from T .

V Set of variables.

V_T Set of variables disjoint from V .

F Set of function symbols.

F_T Set of function symbols disjoint from F .

R Set of relation symbols.

S The set formed by the symbols. $\wedge, \neg, \forall, \square, \square \rightarrow, ($ and $)$.

Definition 5.1 *The set of temporal terms, represented by trm_T , is such that*

- (a) if $t \in T$, then $t \in trm_T$,
- (b) if $t \in V_T$, then $t \in trm_T$,
- (c) if $t_1, \dots, t_n \in trm_T$ and f is a n -ary function belonging to F_T , then $f(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in trm_T$.

Definition 5.2 *The set of non temporal terms, represented by trm_N , is such that*

- (a) if $t \in O_W$, then $t \in \text{trm}_N$,
- (b) if $t \in V$, then $t \in \text{trm}_N$,
- (c) if $t_1, \dots, t_n \in \text{trm}_N$ and f is a n -ary function belonging to F , then $f(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in \text{trm}_N$.

Definition 5.3 The set of terms, represented by D , is such that

- (a) if $t \in \text{trm}_T$, then $t \in D$,
- (b) if $t \in \text{trm}_N$, then $t \in D$.

Definition 5.4 The set of formulas, represented by LT , is the minimum set such that

- (a) if $t, t' \in \text{trm}_T$ and $t = t'$, then $(t = t') \in LT$;
- (b) if $t, t' \in \text{trm}_T$ and $t \geq t'$, then $(t \geq t') \in LT$;
- (c) if $t, t' \in T$ and $t_1, \dots, t_n \in \text{trm}_N$ and r is a n -ary relation symbol belonging to R , then $(t, t', r(t_1, \dots, t_n)) \in LT$;
- (d) if $A, B \in LT$, then $(A \wedge B)$, $\neg A$, $\Box A$ and $(A \Box \rightarrow B)$ belongs to LT ;
- (e) if $A \in LT$ and $v \in (V \cup V_T)$, then $(\forall v)(A) \in LT$.

Definition 5.5 A term ground is a term not containing variables.

Definition 5.6 An atom is a formula written as $r(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ for $r \in R$ and $t_1, \dots, t_n \in \text{trm}_N$.

Definition 5.7 A literal is an atom or the negative of an atom. A positive literal is an atom. A negative literal is the negative of an atom.

Definition 5.8 A sentence is a formula not containing free variables.

Definition 5.9 A base formula is a formula in which the modal operator \Box does not occur.

Definition 5.10 An atomic base formula is a formula written as (t, t', z) , where $t, t' \in T$ and z is a literal.

For $t = t'$, the formula $(t, t', r(t_1, \dots, t_n))$ is written as $(t, r(t_1, \dots, t_n))$; for the interval (t, t') covering all time instants, the formula is written as $(-, r(t_1, \dots, t_n))$. The standard definitions for the symbols \vee , \exists , \equiv , \supset e \diamond are adopted.

5.2 Semantics

Definition 5.11 A model model M is a tuple $\langle T, \leq, U, O_W, R, F', F'_T, G \rangle$ where:

- T Set of nonnegative real numbers $\{t_0, t_1, \dots, t_n, \dots\}$, totally ordered, with first element equal to 0.
- \leq Binary relation on T .
- U Set of possible histories.
- O_W Set of objects that exist in the possible worlds.
- R Set of relations over D .
- F' Set of functions.
- F'_T Set of functions disjoint of F' .

G The tuple $\langle g_1, g_2, g_3, g_4, g_5 \rangle$ of the function, defined as follows.

Definition 5.12 A valuation function G , is a tuple $\langle g_1, g_2, g_3, g_4, g_5 \rangle$ where

$$g_1 : T \rightarrow T,$$

$$g_2 : O_W \rightarrow O_W,$$

$$g_3 : F \rightarrow F',$$

$$g_4 : F_T \rightarrow F'_T,$$

$$g_5 : T \times T \times U \times R \rightarrow R.$$

Definition 5.13 A variable assignment is a function $g_{va} = \langle g_t, g_n \rangle$ where

$$g_t : V_T \rightarrow T,$$

$$g_n : V \rightarrow D.$$

The functions G and g_{va} are used to give logical values, L_v , to the terms:

$$\text{If } t \in T, \text{ then } L_v(t) = g_1(t).$$

$$\text{If } t \in O_W, \text{ then } L_v(t) = g_2(t).$$

$$\text{If } f \in F \text{ and } t = f(t_1, \dots, t_n), \text{ then } L_v(t) = g_3(f)(L_v(t_1), \dots, L_v(t_n)).$$

$$\text{If } f \in F_T \text{ and } t = f(t_1, \dots, t_n), \text{ then } L_v(t) = g_4(f)(L_v(t_1), \dots, L_v(t_n)).$$

$$\text{If } t, t' \in T, u \in U \text{ and } r \in R, \text{ then } L_v(t, t', u, r) = g_5(t, t', u, r)(L_v(t), L_v(t'), L_v(u), L_v(r)).$$

$$\text{If } t \in V_T, \text{ then } L_v(t) = g_t(t).$$

$$\text{If } v \in V, \text{ then for all } t, t' \in D, L_v(t, t', v) = g_7(t, t', v)(L_v(t), L_v(t'), L_v(v)).$$

Let's note that with the next definition the symbols $=$ and \leq are used both syntactically and semantically.

Definition 5.14 The model M , history u and variable assignment g_{va} satisfy a formula A , written as

$$M, u \models_{g_v} A,$$

as follows:

$$(1) M, u \models_{g_v} (t = t') \quad \text{iff} \quad L_v(t) = L_v(t');$$

$$(2) M, u \models_{g_v} (t \leq t') \quad \text{iff} \quad L_v(t) \leq L_v(t');$$

$$(3) M, u \models_{g_v} (t, t', (t_1 = t_2)) \quad \text{iff} \quad L_v(L_v(t), L_v(t'), t_1) = L_v(L_v(t), L_v(t'), t_2);$$

$$(4) M, u \models_{g_v} (t, t', r(t_1, \dots, t_n)) \quad \text{iff}$$

$$\langle L_v((L_v(t), L_v(t'), t_1)), \dots, L_v((L_v(t), L_v(t'), t_n)) \rangle \in g_5(L_v(t), L_v(t'), u, r);$$

$$(5) M, u \models_{g_v} (A \wedge B) \quad \text{iff} \quad M, u \models_{g_v} A \quad \text{and} \quad M, u \models_{g_v} B;$$

$$(6) M, u \models_{g_v} \neg A \quad \text{iff} \quad \nexists(A)(M, u \models_{g_v} A);$$

$$(7) M, u_x \models_{g_v} \Box A \quad (\text{being } A \text{ of the form } (t_i, t_i, \phi) \text{ with } t_i \leq t_i) \quad \text{iff}$$

$$M, u \models_{g_v} A \quad \text{for all } u \in U_i^x;$$

$$(8) M, u \models_{g_v} \forall(z)A \quad \text{iff}$$

$M, u \models_{g_{v'}} A$ for all g'_{va} which differs from g_{va} at most on z ;

(9) $M, u \models_{g_v} (A \square \rightarrow B)$ (being A of the form (t_i, t_j, ϕ_1) and B of the form (t_k, t_l, ϕ_2) with $t_i \leq t_j, t_k \leq t_l$ e $t_i < t_k$) iff

$M, u \models_{g_v} A$ and

$M, u' \models_{g_v} \neg B$ for all u' similar to u for A false.

If $M, u \models_{g_v} A$ for all attribution g_{va} , then writes $M, u \models A$. If $M, u \models A$ for all u , then writes $M \models A$. If A is a sentence and $M, u \models_{g_v} A$ for some g_{va} , then $M, u \models A$.

Considering that $\diamond A$ is $\neg \square(\neg A)$, it has

Definition 5.15 .

$M, u_x \models_{g_v} \diamond A$ (being A of the form (t_i, t_l, ϕ) com $t_l > t_i$) iff

$M, u \models_{g_v} A$ for some $u \in U_i^x$.

Definition 5.16 The formula A is consistent, if

$M, u \models A$

for some M and u .

Definition 5.17 A formula A is true in u and M , if

$M, u \models A$

Definition 5.18 A formula A is valid in the model M , if

$M \models A$.

5.3 Persistence and Causality in the LT

Let A be a formula of the form (t_i, t_j, ϕ_1) with $t_j > t_i$. Comparing the definitions of persistence given in section 4 with the language LT , it has:

1. The formula A persists in u_x at the interval (t_i, t_j) if and only if

$M, u_x \models A$

2. The formula A persists in U_i^x at the interval (t_i, t_j) if and only if

$M, u_x \models \square A$

3. The formula A possibly persists in U_i^x at the interval (t_i, t_j) if and only if

$M, u_x \models \diamond A$

Let B be a formula of the form (t_k, t_l, ϕ_2) with $t_k > t_j$. Comparing the definitions of a cause given in section 3 with the language LT , it has that the formula A is a cause of B in u_x if

$$M, u_x \models A \tag{11}$$

$$M, u_x \models B \tag{12}$$

and

$$M, u_x \models (A \square \rightarrow B) \tag{13}$$

6 Example Cases with the Proposed Model

6.1 Deterministic Process

Scenery 6.1

The Figure 15 shows the upper part of a rectangular flat surface. On the surface and in contact with it there are two rigid balls identified by the numbers 1 and 2. At any given moment each ball can be at rest, moving in uniform rectilinear motion, falling in the pocket, colliding with another ball or with the table boundary. All the collisions are completely elastic. The arrows show the speed direction, the full lines within the rectangle indicate the realized ball trajectories. The point A is in the surface boundary of the table and it is the point that the ball 1 would reach if there was not the ball 2 on the table.

Figure 15: A billiard balls scenario

Let the question be:

Problem 6.1 *Is the collision of the ball 1 with the ball 2 given in Figure 15, a cause for the first ball 1 collision at the point A not occurring?*

From the proposed definition for a cause, this requires:

- (a) the ball 1 collides with the ball 2;
- (b) the ball 1 collision does not collide with the table's boundary in A ;
- (c) if the ball 1 has not collided with the ball 2 the first ball 1 collision would occur in A .

or, considering the propositions

p - the ball 1 collides with the ball 2;

q - the first ball 1 collision does not occur in A

and that u_x is the realized history in Figure 15:

$$M, u_x \models_{gv} p \quad (14)$$

$$M, u_x \models_{gv} q \quad (15)$$

$$M, u_x \models_{gv} (p \square \rightarrow q) \quad (16)$$

The items (a) and (b) are satisfied; the question is the item (c) or the corresponding sentence 16. Let be

$$u_z \in (U - \{u_x\}) \quad (17)$$

such that in u_z the first collision of the ball 1 occurs at the boundary of the table in A . If for $u_z(t_0)$ there exists a very small modification in the position of the ball 2 with relation to $u_x(t_0)$ enough for the two balls not do collide, then u_z is a similar story for u_x : $\neg p$ true. In this case counterfact 16 is true, and hence p is a cause of q . Note that the question is whether the existence of the ball 2 in the path of the ball 1 caused no collision of ball 1 with the edge of the table x ; so the similar story u_x for $\neg p$ requires that only the initial condition of the ball 2 be changed.

Let be the possible histories shown in the Figure 17 for the Boolean network NK of the Figure 16. At the instant t_3 of the history indicated by the red line, the output of the AND is 0, the output of the OR_1 is 1 e and the output of the OR_2 is 0.

Figure 16: A Boolean network NK

Figure 17: Possible histories of the Boolean network NK

- (i) Is the fact of at t_2 the output of OR_2 be 1 cause of at t_3 the output of OR_1 be 1? Among the possible histories, the similar to the realized history (indicated by the red line) is that at t_2 has the world $(0, 1, 0)$ and at t_3 has the world $(0, 0, 1)$, that is, we have in the similar history that the OR_2 is 0 at t_2 and OR_1 is 0 at t_3 , so it is a cause. Let us notice that $(0, 1, 0)$ is closer to $(1, 1, 1)$ than $(0, 0, 0)$.
- (ii) Is, in the instant t_2 , the output of AND equal to 0 cause in t_3 of the output of OR_1 to be equal to 1? Among the possible stories, the similar one to the realized is that at t_2 has the world $(1, 1, 1)$, so in the similar story the OR_1 is 1, so it is not cause.
- (iii) Is, in the instant t_2 , the output of AND equal to 0 cause in t_3 of the output of OR_2 to be equal to 0? There are two possible histories, in the first we have $(t_2, 0, 0, 1)$, $(t_3, 0, 1, 0)$ and in the second one $(t_2, 0, 0, 0)$, $(t_3, 0, 0, 0)$. The similar story has $(t_2, 1, 1, 1)$ and $(t_3, 1, 1, 1)$. So it is cause.

6.2 Nondeterministic Process

Scenery 6.2

Let G be the ball thrower illustrated in Figure 18. If thrower is in the mode 1 of operation, the ball 1 comes out from G to go through a trajectory A ; if it is in the mode 2 of operation when the ball 1 coming out from G , two trajectories with the same probability of occurrence for the ball 1, represented by A and B , are possible. At each one of the trajectories there exists a ball in rest.

Figure 18: The ball thrower

Let the following propositions be:

- $\neg p$ - the ball thrower in mode 1 in t_i ;
- p - the ball thrower in mode 2 in t_i ;
- q - the ball 2 is hit by the ball 1 in t_j ;
- r - the ball 3 is hit by the ball 1 in t_j .

Taking a history u_x where p and q are true, let's have

$$M, u_x \models_{gv} p \tag{18}$$

$$M, u_x \models_{gv} q \tag{19}$$

To be p a cause of q in u_x it is necessary that

$$M, u_x \models_{gv} (p \square \rightarrow q) \tag{20}$$

Let u_y be a history where p and r are true and let u_z be a history where $\neg p$ and r are true. The history u_z is the only one similar in relation to u_x for p false; therefore 20 is true and p is a cause of q . Is p a cause of r in u_y ? In this problem

$$M, u_y \models_{gv} p \tag{21}$$

$$M, u_y \models_{gv} r \tag{22}$$

Considering that u_z is the only similar history in relation to u_y for p false, let's have

$$M, u_y \models_{gv} \neg(p \square \rightarrow r) \tag{23}$$

Therefore p is not a cause of r .

Scenery 6.3

Let be the ball 1 moving from A in a straight line with constant velocity, the object B that can be only at one of the two possible positions (denominated position 1 and position 2 of B), a flat plate C and the ball 2 at rest and positioned in such a manner if (i) B is at the position 1, then the ball 1 rebounds at B and after that hits the ball 2 at the instant t_1 ; (ii) B is at the position 2, then the ball 1 rebounds at C and after that hits the ball 2 at t_2 . The instant t_2 is greater than t_1 . The Figure 19 completes the description of the scenery.

Figure 19: Ball in collision curse with B

Problem 6.2 *Let be the scenery 6.3, the propositions*

p - the ball 1 leaves A in t_i ;

q - the object B is hit by the ball 1 at the position 1;

r - the plate C is hit by the ball 1;

s - the ball 1 hits the ball 2;

and a history u_x with p , q and s . Is q a cause of s in u_x ?

In the case

$$M, u_y \models_v q \quad (24)$$

$$M, u_y \models_v s \quad (25)$$

Let be u_y a history where p and $\neg q$, r and s are true. Provided that u_y is similar in relation to u_x for $\neg q$ true and s is true in u_y , let's have

$$M, u_y \models_v \neg(q \square \rightarrow s) \quad (26)$$

So the theory is silent about if q is a cause of s . Note that if the proposition s is replaced by

a - the ball 1 hits the ball 2 at t_l ,

the counterfactual becomes

$$M, u_y \models_v (q \square \rightarrow a) \quad (27)$$

and q is a cause of a . The reason is that because the path of the ball 1 is greater with B in position 2, the ball 2 will not be reached in t_l .

Problem 6.3 *The Figure 20 represents the realized history, u_x , since the beginning of the 8-puzzle until its ending. Considering that one and only one displacement of the piece is allowed between a given world and another possible world immediately succeeding it and that, for t_j immediately succeeding to t_i and t_k immediately succeeding to t_j , the piece displaced in (t_j, t_k) should be different from the piece displaced in (t_i, t_j) . Let be w_f the world which finishes the game, that the Figure 20 shows as realized in t_3 , and the event*

$e_a(t_0, t_1)$ - the piece 2 is displaced at the interval (t_0, t_1) for the position free in t_0 .

Is the event $e_a(t_0, t_1)$ a cause of the ending of the game in t_3 ?

Figure 20: Move in a game of 8-puzzle

Let be the propositions

p_a - In u_x the piece 2 is displaced in the interval (t_0, t_1) to empty position at t_0 .

p_b - $u_x(t_3) = w_f$.

In the problem

$$M, u_y \models_v p_a \quad (28)$$

$$M, u_y \models_v p_b \quad (29)$$

The Figure 21 shows the realized history and the unrealized histories from t_0 a t_3 ; applying the algorithm 3.1 let's have:

Figure 21: Possible trajectories from the initial state

For $k = 0$, of the trajectories shown in Figure 21, the elements of S are

- $1 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 16$
- $1 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 17$
- $1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 9 \rightarrow 18$
- $1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 9 \rightarrow 19$.

Provided that for the elements of S p_a e p_b are false, let's have

$$M, u_y \models_v (p_a \square \rightarrow p_b) \tag{30}$$

Therefore, p_a is a cause of p_b .

6.3 Simultaneity of Cause and Effect

To consider the question of the simultaneity or not of a cause and its effect let be:

Problem 6.4 *In the seesaw, illustrated by the figure 22, not only the central fulcrum but the plank as well leant on it are rigid bodies. Let be the interval (t_i, t_j) , where t_j immediately succeeds to t_i , the realized events*

- $e_a(t_i, t_j)$ - the left plank's ending descends in the interval (t_i, t_j) ,
- $e_b(t_i, t_j)$ - the right plank's ending rises in the interval (t_i, t_j)

and $p(a)$ and $p(b)$ are propositions that state to be $e_a(t_i, t_j)$ and $e_b(t_i, t_j)$ realized events. Is $p(a)$ a cause of $p(b)$?

Figure 22: The seesaw at the instant t_i

Considering that the events $e_a(t_i, t_j)$ and $e_b(t_i, t_j)$ are simultaneous (section 2) and the temporal relations permitted between the cause and the effect (Figure 9), it has that $p(a)$ is not a cause of $p(b)$. The proposed theory does not admit simultaneous cause and effect. Is it satisfactory? The question is very old, according to Aristotle, for example, the cause does not need to precede its effect, but can be simultaneous - as is the eclipse and the correspondent alignment of the celestial bodies. This standpoint has been widely accepted in the past, there existing, however, exceptions: according to Plato, for example, there is no need of temporal relation between cause and effect. Lewis [5] rejects that a cause should always precede its effects; applying its definition to the problem 6.4 $p(a)$ depends in causal mode on $p(b)$ and $p(b)$ depends on the causal mode on $p(a)$ (if from t_i to t_j the left ending of the board had not descended, then the right ending would not have risen). In other words: $p(a)$ is a cause of $p(a)$. This is counter-intuitive; in the case of seesaw, $p(a)$ and $p(b)$ are aspects of the same event: the balance of the board of the seesaw, they are effects of some common cause. Let be a sinusoidal oscillator (Figure 23).

Figure 23: A sinusoidal oscillator

At stationary state the output is

$$V_o(t) = V \text{sen}(\omega_0 t). \quad (31)$$

Let the oscillator be operating correctly in the u_x and the events

$e_a(t_j, t_k)$ - the signal $V_o(t)$ at stationary state in (t_j, t_k) in u_x

$e_b(t_l, t_m)$ - the signal $V_o(t)$ at stationary state in (t_l, t_m) in u_x

with

$$t_k - t_j \ll \frac{2\pi}{\omega_0} \quad (32)$$

$$t_l - t_j = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_0} \quad (33)$$

and

$$t_m - t_k = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_0} \quad (34)$$

Representing by $p(a)$ and $p(b)$ the propositions that $e_a(t_j, t_k)$ and $e_b(t_l, t_m)$ are true, we have

$$M, u_x \models_v p(a) \quad (35)$$

and

$$M, u_x \models_v p(b) \quad (36)$$

At the instant t_0 the input signal $V_i(t)$ models the thermal oscillator's noise, necessary to auto-start of the oscillator. At stationary state we have

$$0 \ll \frac{V_i(t_0)}{V_i(t_j)} \quad (37)$$

Let us consider u_y the possible history similar to u_x for $p(a)$ false and that $p(b)$ is false in u_y too. In u_y the oscillator is damaged such that $V_o(t)$ at the intervals (t_j, t_k) and (t_l, t_m) took values approximately equal to $V_i(t_0)$, this is the reason for $p(a)$ and $p(b)$ not to be true in u_y . Therefore

$$M, u_x \models_v (p(a) \square \rightarrow p(b)) \quad (38)$$

and $p(a)$ is a cause of $p(b)$. It should be noted that in this case there exists no cause acting on itself, but there is a cause whose effect acts, at a posterior temporal interval, in a way similar to its cause.

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